

THE LOOP ENSEMBLE - OPEN SOURCE INSTRUMENTS FOR TEACHING ELECTRONIC MUSIC IN THE CLASSROOM

Christof Martin Schultz

Technische Universität Berlin
c.schultz@campus.tu-berlin.de
christofmschultz@gmail.com

Marten Seedorf

Technische Universität Berlin, 3DMIN Project
marten.seedorf@campus.tu-berlin.de
drahtsalat@joyscouts.de

ABSTRACT

The electronic production, processing and dissemination of music is an essential part of the contemporary, digitalized music culture. Digital media play an important role for children and adolescents in their everyday handling of music. These types of media call for an active participation instead of mere reception and thus offer new ways of musical socialization. Despite their cultural relevance and being lively discussed in German music education, these aspects still are marginalized in the educational practice in German classrooms. In the context of the interdisciplinary research project 3DMIN, we developed the loop ensemble. It consists of three virtual instruments and is designed for the practical pedagogical dissemination of electronic music and its technical basics. The ensemble is released as an Open Educational Resource. We evaluated the instruments' usability in three ways. They were cross-checked with relevant ISO standards, three workshops were held and the participants interviewed and, finally, an accompanying analysis using the GERD model was performed, focusing gender and diversity aspects. The results show a distinct practical suitability of the ensemble, yet further empirical research is needed for a profound evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

This article deals with an exemplary approach to integrate digital media in general and electronic music in particular¹ into German music classrooms: The loop ensemble. In the context of the 3DMIN project², we developed three virtual music instruments in Pure Data. These Open Educational Resources³ are designed as didactic material for

¹ This abstraction is a result of the discourse within German music education, where we do not see a specific consideration of electronic music and its instruments. Instead, they are a rather marginalized part of a greater discussion, that deals with digital media in contemporary music culture and their possibilities and problems for music education as a whole.

² *Design, Development and Dissemination of New Musical Instruments*, an interdisciplinary between Technische Universität Berlin and Berlin University of the Arts. See <http://www.3dmin.org>.

³ Open Educational Resources (OER) are „digitised materials offered freely and openly for educators, students, and self-learners to use and reuse for teaching, learning, and research“ [1].

an action-oriented music education in combination with autonomous learning, focusing electronic music culture, its aesthetics and technical principles.

2. BACKGROUND

The production, performance, storing, processing and the dissemination of music as well as listening to it are and always have been technologically determined [2]. Consequently, innovations of sound within its cultural context are often caused by technological changes [3]. In the end, the listeners are affected by these processes in various ways. The dynamic symbiosis is intensified by the progressing digitalization and in this sense digital media and their technology define the current reality of music culture [4]. Children and adolescents grow up in this cultural environment, their perception and handling of music is pervaded by digital technology. It is a distinctive characteristic of digital media, that they facilitate cultural participation in comparison to certain older forms of media. They constantly encourage users to actively shape music culture [5]. But this potential also brings challenges. For example, the users could be confronted with the complexity of a medially globalized music culture and develop a need for orientation, for a deeper understanding. The irrelevance of the own contribution within the vast mass of medial information can carry frustration. These problems illustrate the importance of media literacy in a digitalized music culture and the need of educational institutions to integrate these technocultural aspects [6].

German music education tends to be conservative. Usually, the preservation of cultural traditions is favored over the integration of cultural changes, especially if they concern medial or technological aspects of music. So, a skeptical distance from digitalization was kept for a long time [7]. Not until the beginning of the new millennium an ideological debate on basic principles led into a pragmatic handling of the topic. Impulses were sent towards educational policy, academical training and didactic practice within the classrooms, proposing feasible ways for the integration of digital media [8]. These were and are being implemented, but not extensively and often hesitantly [7]. In spite of these changes, digital music culture still is not a crucial part of German music education [9]. Yet, a fundamental willingness to update music education seems to exist, since curricula contain many formulations that stress the relevance of digital media [7, 10, 11]. The need to integrate digital music culture seems to be approved when its

relevance in the contemporary living worlds of the pupils is considered. This basic will for change is put into perspective by the stable status quo in educational practice and this might be why the pedagogical discourse has lost its intensity since the middle of the first century [8]. Main obstacles, that were regularly described, are the teacher's lack of skills or experience dealing with digital music media, as well as the high cost and the complexity of music software [12]. As a result, younger pedagogical research in this field concentrates on the quality of learning software [8, 13, 14]. Professional music software shows severe problems when it is used in music classrooms [8] and in this regard, pedagogically adequate software is rare. There is still a need for theoretical and conceptual reflections dealing with technology, an applicable didactic and concrete proposals and examples for the use of digital media in the classroom [15].

3. THE LOOP ENSEMBLE

With the development of loop we tried to create an exemplary model of suitable music software for use in the classroom that tries to fulfill the various demands mentioned previously. As computer-based instruments loop attempts to offer the possibility to integrate digital media with a focus on electronic music culture and its technology. Loop consists of three independent but connectable electronic instruments made in Pure Data: ADD, DRUMBO and JERRY (see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). They use different controllers, are based on different methods of sound synthesis and differentiate in their musical roles.

Figure 1: Main interface of ADD

Firstly, the issue of cost had to be taken into account. The loop instruments do this by completely relying on open source software and by being released under the General Public License (GNU GPLv3) itself, which guarantees users the freedoms to run, study, share and modify the software. The absence of licensing fees results in a zero purchase price for developers and users. Additionally, the optional hardware controllers are available for a relatively low price of approximately 50 Euros each. Open Source means flexibility and freedom in using, customizing and sharing the software. Thereby the loop ensemble meets the requirements of the current call of the German Federal Ministry of

Figure 2: Main interface of DRUMBO

Education and Research for Open Educational Resources [16].

Another urgent demand regarding music software in the classroom is the reduction of complexity [12]. Reacting to this, our basic concept of the three instruments intends that they should be able to self-describe their technical principles through interaction. To achieve this, the loop instruments are equipped with so-called illustration patches (see Fig. 3). These are subroutines, small interfaces within the interface, that use the instruments main engine but focus on a particular functionality like pitch, sequencing, reverb, frequency modulation, amplitude modulation, ADSR envelopes, etc. With interactive minimal examples and short text blocks the patches try to explain the function of the specific modules, audio-technical basics and special phenomena. They can be opened directly from the main interface and allow the users to playfully and interactively experience individual features.

Figure 3: Illustration patch visualizing and interactively explaining waveforms within the instrument DRUMBO

The experiences obtained and conclusions drawn from the patches are meant to be used creatively when using loop as an instrument. This way the learning process is closely tied to a creative musical practice and it is this connection that makes the ensemble suitable for action-oriented lessons.

During the development we constantly had to find a balance between restricting the technical complexity in terms of the educational objectives and implementing interesting functionalities that expanded the musical possibilities.

Due to the frequently mentioned problems expressed in the pedagogical discourse we often decided to choose simplicity over functionality. Getting started with loop is particularly low-threshold. The automation established by the sequencers aids users to get started and play without a long period of training. With experience or after exploring the patches the instruments have the potential to lead to a more complex and elaborate style of play.

Connecting the three instruments with each other using the network functionality creates the ensemble, which establishes a rhythmic and harmonic synchronization that enables small groups to play together. This way loop allows intuitive cooperation and supports collective musical improvisation, making the ensemble suitable for action-oriented group lessons. This application of the ensemble is sustained by easy access and early senses of achievement, that are made possible by effective and clearly laid out controls, the optional usage of rhythmic or tonal grids, presets and sequencing: Jamming EDM with the ensemble is designed to be easy and fun, even or especially for beginners. Here ADD, DRUMBO and JERRY can loosely be assigned to musical roles: Bass, drums and pad/lead. However, these borders are quickly surmountable due to their ambivalent sound production.

The instruments are designed to support diverse traditions of electronic music. The interconnection of the three instruments enables students to play different styles of electronic dance music, depending on the adjustable aesthetic of the sounds and the settings for the rhythmic parameters. Also, loop is meant to motivate the students to experiment freely, for example by designing unusual sounds and arrangements outside of rhythmic or harmonic boundaries. Since the authors regard the breaking of barriers between musical styles as a catalyst for musical development, the loop ensemble is meant to motivate the blending of different approaches. There is no default mode. The harmonic grids and/or rhythmic synchronization can be switched on or off according to the individual user's approach and objective. Still, the possibility to produce more popular styles of electronic dance music with clear tonal and rhythmic patterns was implemented to meet the assumed preferences of the target group.

Optionally, the instruments can be controlled with low-cost hardware controllers. These are a KORG nanoKONTROL2 and an Akai LPD8. The third instrument JERRY is controlled entirely with keyboard and mouse. The graphical interfaces are adapted to the appearance of the associated controllers to help understanding their layout. All instruments can be controlled in full without the controllers using mouse and keyboard.

Due to the educational context, we tried to use appropriate language, for example with everyday analogies, that still include the technical terminologies. At the moment the ensemble only exists in German. If requested, an English version easily realizable.

The used framework Pure Data is a visual programming language that uses data flow of objects connected by patches. This is related to analog synthesizer patches and quickly enables users to get started and provides an intuitive way of

programming. Pure Data is development and application environment at the same time. Building the instruments circuitry and actively using the instrument is both happening in the same window. Every change is compiled and executed in real-time, which provides direct feedback, but can also lead to deadlocks and crashes. Main advantage of Pure Data is its visual character that makes it suitable for educational use. Additionally it comes with a easy to learn and easy to use interface, plenty of libraries and a strong community. A noticeable negative effect on the usability arises from the rudimentary and limited possibilities that Pure Data offers developers for designing the user interfaces. Also the proximity of development and application environment is risky, since users can unintentionally damage primary functionalities.

To further facilitate the use of loop, the system requirements are kept to a minimum. Even ten-year-old computer hardware with any major operating system (Windows, Mac OS X, Ubuntu Linux) should be able to run the instruments smoothly. For an optimal experience and the output of lower frequencies active loudspeakers or quality headphones are highly recommended.

In summary, the didactical concept of the loop ensemble includes interactivity and stresses a self-explanatory approach. Its focus lies on self-determined and action-oriented learning. Due to its capacity to be used as an ensemble via network connection, it is also suitable for group lessons in the classroom. To support chalk-and-talk teaching as well, loop is released with an additional version, of which the interface is optimized for presentation situations. In general, the ensemble follows the formula „low threshold, high ceiling“ [17]. On the one hand loop offers an easy access to the shaping and understanding of electronic music and allows beginners or even non-musician to express themselves musically. On the other hand, it is also capable of complex musical actions and offers a deeper insight into the technical principles behind electronic sound-synthesis, for example through the exploration of the code of the instruments.

4. EVALUATION

We put the instruments through three phases of evaluation. At first we applied a rating system for music software utilized in educational contexts that uses basic ISO norms on the subject usability [8]. The results show that loop positively stands out in exploration, self-descriptiveness and suitability for learning. However, it shows deficiencies in fault tolerance and controllability in comparison with commercial products.

The second evaluation was exploratory and began while the instruments were still under development. We used them in workshops to evaluate their usability and suitability in educational contexts. For an easy access to the target group we got in contact with university support programs for girls provided by the Technische Universität Berlin and the Freie Universität Berlin. The chosen target group for the instruments, students in the upper secondary, was approached in three independent workshops (N = 10). In

those two-hour sessions the students could freely experiment with the instruments (see Fig. 4). We cautiously assisted their exploration of the ensemble by answering questions and providing suggestions. Every workshop ended

Figure 4: Full setup of loop’s instrument DRUMBO with the Akai LPD8 Controller

with a group interview following a guideline. The guideline covered the subjects: Innovation, fun, usability and integration potential. The results were quite promising and provided us with valuable feedback to optimize the usability. The majority of the participants considered the instruments as desirable for their music classes. They especially valued the activity-oriented possibility to experiment and the visual presentation. The workshops also had a noticeable influence on the design and features of the instruments. The automated sequencers in ADD and DRUMBO seemed to help restrained students to start using and experimenting with the instruments. The early version of JERRY that was used in the workshops was lacking a sequencer. The students seemed to treat it with more reservation and caution. After the workshops we integrated this crucial feature to improve accessibility.

Conscious and unconscious decisions made by software developers often lead to a selective reproduction of some aspects of reality implemented in the software, while others are ignored or neglected [18]. Therefore software always has the capacity to affect sociocultural, ethical and political values and to influence the thinking and acting of users. To sufficiently deal with this, we considered a third accompanying evaluation. We used the *Gender Extended Research and Development* (GERD) analysis model, which tries to encourage developers to reflect their design choices at all critical sections of the research process and the development [19]. With its list of questions we became aware of excluded user groups, reflected about the main beneficiaries and realized how our personal background affected the development.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Ultimately, the three evaluations helped us to adopt varied perspectives and thereby improved the development of the instruments. With the valuation model of Ahlers that uses ISO usability norms we could identify innovative strengths and expectable shortcomings that came with the rudimentary open source software Pure Data. To eliminate these disadvantages we would have had to refrain from Pure Data. This would most likely have resulted in instruments that are limited in their openness, flexibility and accessibility.

The explorative workshop evaluation still showed us that the instrument appear to be usable in a classroom context. A focused evaluation of the loop ensemble in school-based practice which captures its actual suitability remains still pending. At the moment we are developing an implementation strategy at schools. We plan to organize workshops or even long-term instrumental lessons in electronic music. The didactic concepts will reflect the flexibility of the ensemble. According to our experience the best educational results are achieved with a balanced mixture of presentations (using the dedicated presentation version of the ensemble) and action-oriented sections, where the pupils are able to act and learn autonomously using the instruments. Also, we hope to be able to train teachers in the use of the ensemble and its educational content, enabling them to integrate electronic music into their lessons. Finally, we call on teachers and students to freely use, distribute and modify the loop ensemble. Loop and its manual can be downloaded free of charge at the PD Community Portal.⁴

6. REFERENCES

- [1] OECD, “Giving Knowledge for Free.” 2007.
- [2] A. Smudits, “Musik in der digitalen Mediamorphose,” in *Musik/Medien/Kunst - Wissenschaftliche und künstlerische Perspektiven*, B. Flath, Ed. Bielefeld: transcript, 2013, pp. 75–96.
- [3] B. Enders, “Vom Idiophon zum Touchpad. Die musik-technologische Entwicklung zum virtuellen Musikinstrument,” in *Musik/Medien/Kunst - Wissenschaftliche und künstlerische Perspektiven*, B. Flath, Ed. Bielefeld: transcript, 2013, pp. 55–74.
- [4] P. Tschmuck, “Elektronische Musik - von der Avantgarde-Nische zum paradigmatischen Musikstil,” in *Musik/Medien/Kunst - Wissenschaftliche und künstlerische Perspektiven*, B. Flath, Ed. Bielefeld: transcript, 2013, pp. 97–109.
- [5] M. Gall, G. Sammer, and A. de Vugt (Eds.), “Introduction to New Media in the Classroom,” in *European Perspectives on Music Education: New Media in the Classroom*, ser. EAS publications. Innsbruck: Helbling, 2012, pp. 11–30.

⁴ <https://puredata.info/Members/loop2016> accessed: July 11, 2016.

- [6] T. Münch, "Medien im Musikunterricht," in *Musik-Didaktik: Praxishandbuch für die Sekundarstufe I und II*, W. Jank, Ed. Berlin: Cornelsen, 2013, pp. 220–228.
- [7] N. Schläbitz, "Musik-Medien und die Musikpädagogik. Eine Romanze mit manchmal tragischen Momenten und ungewissem Ausgang," in preparation, in: Rolf Großmann, Elena Ungeheuer (Ed.): *Musik und Medien. Laaber-Reihe: Kompendium der Musikwissenschaft, Basiswissen Musik*.
- [8] M. Ahlers, *Schnittstellen-Probleme im Musikunterricht: Fachhistorische und empirische Studien zum Einsatz und zur Ergonomie von Sequenzer-Programmen*, ser. Forum Musikpädagogik: Augsburger Schriften. Augsburg: Wißner, 2009, vol. 89.
- [9] —, "Information Communication Technology as Creativity Support Tools?: On German Music Educations History in ICT: Selected Research and Recent Developments," in *European Perspectives on Music Education: New Media in the Classroom*, M. Gall, G. Sammer, and A. de Vugt, Eds. Innsbruck: Helbling, 2012, pp. 125–134.
- [10] Berliner Landesinstitut für Schule und Medien LISUM, "Rahmenlehrplan für die Sekundarstufe I - Musik." 2006, accessed: July 11, 2016. [Online]. Available: http://www.berlin.de/imperia/md/content/sen-bildung/schulorganisation/lehrplaene/sek1_musik.pdf
- [11] —, "Rahmenlehrplan für die gymnasiale Oberstufe - Musik." 2006, accessed: July 11, 2016. [Online]. Available: http://www.berlin.de/imperia/md/content/sen-bildung/unterricht/lehrplaene/sek2_musik.pdf
- [12] G. Sammer, M. Gall, and N. Breeze, "Using music software at school: The European framework," *NET MUSIC Project 1.*, pp. 155–177, 2009.
- [13] M. Stubenvoll, *Musiklernen am Computer: Zur Qualität von Musik-Lernsoftware und ihrer empirischen Überprüfung*, ser. Musikpädagogik in der Blauen Eule. Essen: Die Blaue Eule, 2008, vol. 81.
- [14] B. Weidler, *Computersoftware im Musikunterricht: Am Beispiel von „Band-in-a-Box“*. Hamburg: Diplomica, 2014.
- [15] C. Albers, J. Magenheimer, and D. Meister, "Der Einsatz digitaler Medien als Herausforderung von Schule - eine Annäherung," in *Schule in der digitalen Welt. Medienpädagogische Ansätze und Schulforschungsperspektiven*, D. Meister, Ed. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag, 2011, pp. 7–18.
- [16] Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, "Richtlinie zur Förderung von Offenen Bildungsmaterialien (Open Educational Resources - OERinfo). Bundesanzeiger vom 15.01.2016," Berlin, 2016, accessed: July 11, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bmbf.de/foerderungen/bekanntmachung.php?B=1132>
- [17] M. Resnick, B. Myers, K. Nakakoji, B. Shneiderman, R. Pausch, S. Ted, and M. Eisenberg, "Design principles for tools to support creative thinking," in *Creativity Support Tools - A workshop sponsored by the National Science Foundation*, B. Shneiderman, G. Fischer, M. Czerwinski, B. Myers, and M. Resnick, Eds. National Science Foundation, 2005, pp. 25–35, accessed: July 11, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.cs.umd.edu/hcil/CST/Papers/designprinciples.pdf>
- [18] C. Bath, "De-gendering informatischer artefakte: Grundlagen einer kritisch-feministischen technikgestaltung," Ph.D. dissertation, Fachbereich Mathematik und Informatik, Universität Bremen, 2009.
- [19] C. Draude, S. Maaß, and K. Wajda, "Gender-/Diversity-Aspekte in der Informatikforschung: Das GERD-Modell," in *Gender-UseIT. HCI, Web-Usability und UX unter Gendersichtspunkten*, N. Marsden and U. Kempf, Eds. Berlin: de Gruyter, 2014, pp. 67–78.